

Synthesis of Oxygen Heterocyclics from 2-Hydroxy Fluorene and 2-Hydroxy Fluorenone

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The synthesis of 3'-methyl and 2'-methyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan from 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorene and 2-hydroxy-1-allyl fluorene respectively and their 9-oxo derivatives from the corresponding fluorenone derivatives has been described.

Fluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone and its 4'-methoxy derivative have been synthesised from 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorene through condensation with benzaldehyde and anisaldehyde respectively and the simultaneous cyclisation and dehydrogenation of the fluorenyl styryl ketones obtained. 9-Oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone and its 4'-methoxy derivative have been similarly obtained from 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorenone. The Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorene has also been studied.

ONLY a few oxygen heterocyclics from fluorene and fluorenone are known^{1,2}. The present work deals with the synthesis of some fluoreno and 9-oxofluoreno furan and γ -pyrone derivatives.

2-Hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorene was synthesised according to Bergmann and Berlin³. To give additional proof for the structure the methyl ether of this compound was oxidised to the corresponding fluorenone derivative and this was condensed with hydrazine hydrate when a pyridazine derivative was obtained.

2-Hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorene was condensed with ethyl bromo acetate and 2-carbethoxymethoxy-1-acetyl fluorene obtained was hydrolysed to the corresponding acid. It was heated with freshly fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride to get 3'-methyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan (Ia).

2-Allyloxyfluorene was subjected to rearrangement according to Lothrop⁴. Instead of the two products reported, only one could be isolated in a workable yield. This was 2-hydroxy-1-allylfluorene, as on methylation and oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate it gave the same acid as the one obtained by the haloform reaction on 2-methoxy-1-acetyl fluorenone. The hydroxy allyl derivative was acetylated and then brominated with one mole of bromine. The dibromo derivative obtained was then converted into 2'-methyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan (Ib) by refluxing with alcoholic potassium cyanide.

When 2-acetoxyfluorenone was subjected to Fries rearrangement according to Bergmann and Berlin³, only the deacetylated product could be isolated. The m.p. of 2-hydroxy-1-acetylfluorenone and the m.p. and the analysis of the pyridazine derivative

Ia	R	R'
Ib	CH ₃	H

IIa	R	R'
IIb	H	C ₆ H ₅
IIc	CH ₃	H

IIIa	R	R'
IIIb	CH ₃	COCH ₃
IIIc	C ₆ H ₅	H
IIId	p-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	H

IVa	R=C ₆ H ₅
IVb	R=p-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃

reported by these authors agree more or less with the m.p. and the analysis of 2-hydroxyfluorenone and its hydrazone respectively. However, when this rearrangement was carried out at 140° we obtained a compound which gave the tests for a hydroxy ketone. To this compound 2-hydroxy-1-acetylfluorenone structure is assigned because its methyl ether was found to be identical with 2-methoxy-1-acetylfluorenone obtained by the oxidation of 2-methoxy-1-acetylfluorene.

2-Hydroxy-1-acetylfluorenone was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and the carbethoxymethoxy derivative was hydrolysed to the acid. On heating with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate it gave 3'-methyl 9-oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan (IIa).

2-Hydroxyfluorenone was benzoylated and subjected to Fries rearrangement. The hydroxy ketone was methylated and this on heating with one mole of hydrazine hydrate in alcohol gave a pyridazine derivative as seen from the analytical data. Therefore 2-hydroxy-1-benzoyl fluorenone structure is assigned to the hydroxy ketone. Through the same sequence of reactions as above it was converted into 3'-phenyl-9-oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan (IIb).

2-Hydroxy fluorenone was condensed with allyl bromide. The allyloxy compound on heating to 230° gave a hydroxy allyl derivative. This was acetylated and then brominated with exactly one mole of bromine. The dibromide obtained was cyclised to a furan derivative by refluxing with alcoholic potassium cyanide. On reduction with hydrazine hydrate and potassium hydroxide in ethoxy ethanol it gave 2'-methyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan (Ib). Therefore the hydroxy allyl compound is assigned 2-hydroxy-1-allyl fluorenone structure and 2'-methyl-9-oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan (IIc) structure is assigned to the furan derivative.

2-Hydroxy-1-acetylfluorene on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation gave a product which analysed for $C_{19}H_{14}O_3$ and has been assigned 3'-acetyl-2'-methyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone (IIIa) structure. Attempts at deacetylation did not succeed. Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation of 2-hydroxy-1-acetylfluorene did not give any pure product but the synthesis of 2'-phenylfluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone was achieved through another route.

2-Hydroxy-1-acetylfluorene was condensed with benzaldehyde in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide. The product obtained gave a blue colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, a deep red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid and a positive Wilson test⁵. Moreover, it gave an acetyl derivative indicating that the hydroxyl group was free and no cyclisation had occurred. Therefore, 2-hydroxy-1-fluorenyl styryl ketone structure is assigned to the product. On refluxing with selenium dioxide in iso-amyl alcohol it gave 2'-phenyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone (IIIb). That the methylene group in the 9-position of fluorene is not oxidised is evident from

the analytical data and the fact that the compound was different from the product obtained from 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorenone through a similar series of reactions.

2-Hydroxy-1-acetylfluorene on a similar condensation with anisaldehyde gave 2-hydroxy-1-fluorenyl *p*-methoxy styryl ketone which on boiling with selenium dioxide in iso-amyl alcohol gave 2'-(*p*-methoxy phenyl) fluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone (IIIc).

2-Hydroxy-1-acetylfluorenone on condensation with benzaldehyde in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide gave a product to which 2-hydroxy 9-oxo-1-fluorenyl styryl ketone structure is assigned on the basis of its colour reactions and the formation of an acetyl derivative. On refluxing with selenium dioxide in iso-amyl alcohol it gave 2'-phenyl 9-oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone (IVa).

2-Hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorenone on a similar condensation with anisaldehyde gave 2-hydroxy 9-oxo-1-fluorenyl *p*-methoxy styryl ketone, which was converted into 2'-(*p*-methoxy phenyl)-9-oxo-fluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone (IVb) with selenium dioxide in iso-amyl alcohol.

Experimental

2-Methoxy-1-acetyl fluorene: 2-Hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorene (0.5 g.) in dry acetone (20 ml.) was refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml.) for 4 hr. The solvent was removed and the residue was diluted with water. The separated solid crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colourless needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 154°. (Found C, 80.67; H, 5.75. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 80.67; H, 5.88%).

2-Methoxy-1-acetyl fluorenone: The above methyl ether (0.5 g.) was refluxed with sodium dichromate (2 g.) in acetic acid on a sand bath for 1 hr. It was then diluted with water and the separated solid was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 179°–80°. (Found: C, 75.94; H, 4.46. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.19; H, 4.76%).

The pyridazine derivative: 2-Methoxy-1-acetyl fluorenone (1 g.) was refluxed in alcohol (150 ml.) with hydrazine hydrate (85% ; 0.2 ml.) on a steam bath for 8 hr. The solvent was removed by distillation and the mixture diluted with water. The solid crystallised from benzene in yellow cubes (0.5 g.), m.p. 238°. (Found: N, 11.25. $C_{16}H_{11}ON_2$ requires N, 11.29%).

2-Carbethoxymethoxy-1-acetylfluorene: A mixture of 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorene (1 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) and ethyl bromoacetate (1 ml.) in dry acetone (40 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr. The solvent was removed, and water was added. The separated solid crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in colourless needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 73.06; H, 5.72. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 73.53; H, 5.80%).

2-Carboxymethoxy-1-acetyl fluorene : The above ester (1 g.) was heated with sodium hydroxide (5%; 20 ml.) on a steam bath for 2 hr. The product obtained on acidification crystallised from ethyl acetate in colourless cubes (0.4 g.), m.p. 201° (decomp.). Found : C, 71.98; H, 4.72. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.35; H, 4.96%.

3'-Methyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan : The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed with freshly fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.) on a sand bath for 1 hr. The solid separating on adding the reaction mixture to ice crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless flakes (0.2 g.), m.p. 124°–25°. (Found : C, 87.02; H, 5.31. $C_{16}H_{12}O$ requires C, 87.28; H, 5.45%.)

2-Methoxy-1-allyl fluorene : *2-Hydroxy-1-allyl fluorene*⁴ (1 g.) was refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (1 ml.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) on a steam bath for 2 hr. The methyl ether crystallised from petroleum ether in colourless needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 62°. (Found : C, 86.56; H, 6.79. $C_{17}H_{16}O$ requires C, 86.44; H, 6.78%.)

2-Methoxy fluorenone-1-carboxylic acid : A solution of 2-methoxy-1-acetyl fluorenone (1 g.) in dioxane was slowly added to a solution of sodium hypobromite (prepared from 3 g. of sodium hydroxide and 3 g. of bromine) with constant stirring and the solution was stirred at 40°–50° for 8 hr. Excess of hypobromite was destroyed by adding sodium sulphite and the dioxane was then removed. The solution was filtered and acidified. The solid obtained crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow flakes (0.4 g.), m.p. 241°. (Found : C, 70.79; H, 3.62. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.87; H, 3.93%.)

The same product was obtained when a mixture of 2-methoxy-1-allyl fluorene (1 g.), sodium hydroxide (5%; 25 ml.) and potassium permanganate (1 g.) was heated on a water bath at 50°–60° for 15 hr. and the solution was filtered, the filtrate decolourised by adding sodium bisulphite and acidified with hydrochloric acid.

2-Acetoxy-1-allyl fluorene : *2-Hydroxy-1-allyl fluorene* (0.5 g.) was acetylated as usual with fused sodium acetate (1 g.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.) and crystallised from petroleum ether in colourless cubes (0.4 g.), m.p. 184°. (Found : C, 81.83; H, 6.32. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 81.83; H, 6.02%.)

2-Acetoxy-1-allyl fluorene dibromide : *2-Acetoxy-1-allyl fluorene* (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) and cooled to 15°–20°. Bromine (0.6 g.) in acetic acid (5 ml.) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The separated product was crystallised from petroleum ether in colourless needles (1 g.), m.p. 153°. (Found : C, 50.94; H, 3.77; Br, 37.71. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2Br_2$ requires C, 50.77; H, 3.58; Br, 37.75%.)

2-Methyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan : The above dibromide (1 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (50 ml.) and potassium cyanide (1.5 g.) in alcohol (15 ml.)

was added. The mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 3 hr. The solid obtained on removal of the solvent crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 151°–52°. (Found : C, 87.16; H, 5.48. $C_{16}H_{12}O$ requires C, 87.28; H, 5.45%.)

2-Hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorenone : *2-Acetoxyfluorenone* (2 g.) was heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) in an oil bath at 140°–50° for 4 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual crystallised from acetic acid in brown needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 250°–51°. (Found : C, 74.87; H, 4.16. $C_{15}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 75.11; H, 4.20%.)

On methylation with dimethyl sulphate by refluxing in acetone solution in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate it gave the methyl ether identical with 2-methoxy-1-acetyl fluorenone described earlier.

2-Carbethoxymethoxy-1-acetyl fluorenone : A mixture of 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorenone (1 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) and ethyl bromoacetate (1 ml.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 4 hr. The product obtained on working up as before crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow needles (0.9 g.), m.p. 174°. (Found : C, 70.73; H, 5.40. $C_{19}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 70.37; H, 4.94%.)

2-Carboxymethoxy-1-acetyl fluorenone : The above ester (1 g.) was heated with sodium hydroxide (5%; 25 ml.) on a steam bath for 4 hr. The product obtained on acidification with conc. hydrochloric acid crystallised from acetic acid in brown cubes (0.4 g.), m.p. 252° (decomp.). (Found : C, 68.87; H, 4.16. $C_{17}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 68.92; H, 4.05%.)

3'-Methyl-9-oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan : The above acid (1 g.) was refluxed with freshly fused sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.) on a sand bath for 2 hr. It was then added to ice. The separated solid was crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 140°–41°. (Found : C, 81.77; H, 4.13. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 82.06; H, 4.27%.)

2-Benzoyloxy fluorenone : Benzoyl chloride (1 ml) was added to a well cooled solution of 2-hydroxyfluorenone (1 g.) in sodium hydroxide (10%; 25 ml.) and the reaction mixture was shaken vigorously. The separated solid crystallised from acetic acid in yellow flakes (0.9 g.), m.p. 177°. (Found : C, 79.63; H, 3.87. $C_{20}H_{12}O_3$ requires, C, 80.00; H, 4.00%.)

2-Hydroxy-1-benzoyl fluorenone : The above compound (2 g.) was heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) in an oil bath at 140°–150° for 4 hr. The product obtained on adding ice and hydrochloric acid crystallised from acetic acid in brown needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 173°. (Found : C, 79.88; H, 3.51. $C_{20}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 80.00; H, 4.00%.)

2-Methoxy-1-benzoyl fluorenone : The above hydroxy ketone (0.5 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone with anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml.) on a steam bath for 4 hr. The solid obtained on working up as usual crystallised from dilute acetic acid in orange needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 212°. (Found : C, 79.76; H, 4.22. $C_{21}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 80.26; H, 4.45%).

The pyridazine derivative : 2-Methoxy-1-benzoyl fluorenone (1 g.) in alcohol (100 ml.) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (0.2 ml.) on a steam bath for 8 hr. The solvent was removed and the residue was diluted with water. The separated solid crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in yellow needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 210°. (Found : N, 8.95. $C_{21}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 9.03%).

2-Carboethoxymethoxy-1-benzoyl fluorenone : 2-Hydroxy-1-benzoyl fluorenone (1 g.) in dry acetone (100 ml.) was refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) and ethyl bromoacetate (1 ml.) for 6 hr. The solid obtained on working up as before crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow needles (0.8 g.) m.p. 176°–77°. (Found : C, 74.69; H, 4.94. $C_{24}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 74.61; H, 4.63%).

2-Carboxymethoxy-1-benzoyl fluorenone : The above ester (2 g.) was heated on a steam bath with sodium hydroxide (10%; 50 ml.) for 2 hr. The product obtained on acidification with conc. hydrochloric acid crystallised from acetic acid in brown needles (0.9 g.), m.p. 220°. (Found : C, 73.59; H, 4.03. $C_{22}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 73.74; H, 3.91%).

3'-Phenyl 9-oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan : The above acid (1 g.) was refluxed with fused sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride for 1 hr. The solid obtained on pouring the reaction mixture on ice crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 154°–55°. (Found : C, 85.12; H, 4.18. $C_{21}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 85.13; H, 4.05%).

2-Allyloxy fluorenone : A mixture of 2-hydroxy fluorenone (2 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (4 g.) and allyl bromide (2 ml.) was refluxed in dry acetone on a steam bath for 15 hr. The solvent was removed and the residue was added to water. The separated solid was washed with sodium hydroxide and water. It crystallised from alcohol in golden yellow needles (1.5 g.), m.p. 84°. (Found : C, 81.66; H, 5.37. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 81.36; H, 5.08%).

2-Hydroxy-1-allyl fluorenone : 2-Allyloxy fluorenone (1 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 230°–35° for 5 min. It was then cooled and extracted with 25 ml. of 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The solid obtained on acidification of the alkaline extract crystallised from dilute alcohol in red needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 145°. (Found : C, 81.39; H, 5.27. $C_{16}H_{17}O_2$ requires C, 81.36; H, 5.08%).

2-Acetoxy-1-allyl fluorenone : Prepared from 2-hydroxy-1-allyl fluorenone as usual and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture (0.9 g.) gave m.p. 129°. (Found : C, 78.00; H, 5.24. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 78.27; H, 5.07%).

2-Acetoxy-1-allyl fluorenone dibromide : To a solution of 2-acetoxy-1-allyl fluorenone (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml.) cooled to 15°–20° bromine (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml.) was added dropwise with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for further one hour. The separated solid crystallised from benzene in yellow needles (1.1 g.) m.p. 194°. (Found : C, 49.53; H, 3.00. Br, 36.93. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3Br_2$ requires C, 49.32; H, 3.33; Br, 36.53%).

2'-Methyl 9-oxofluorenone (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan : The above dibromide (1 g.) in alcohol (75 ml.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide (1.5 g.) in alcohol (25 ml.) for 3 hr. Alcohol was removed and the residue was diluted with water. The separated solid crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 148°. (Found : C, 82.13; H, 4.17. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 82.06; H, 4.27%).

Reduction : The above furan (0.5 g.) dissolved in ethoxy ethanol (25 ml.) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (85%; 2 ml.) for 1 hr. Potassium hydroxide (2 g.) was then added and the heating was continued for 6 hr. The solid obtained on adding the reaction mixture to water crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 148°. Mixed m.p. with 2'-methyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 5', 4') furan described above was not depressed.

2'-Methyl-3'-acetyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone : A mixture of 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorenone (1.5 g.), acetic anhydride (3 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (3 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 180°–90° for 10 hr. It was then added to ice and the separated solid crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 242°. (Found : C, 78.41; H, 5.00. $C_{19}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 78.61; H, 4.83%).

2-Hydroxy-1-fluorenyl styryl ketone : 2-Hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorenone (1.5 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (100 ml.) and potassium hydroxide (7 g. in 7 ml. water) and benzaldehyde (1.5 ml.) were added. The mixture was left for 24 hr. and then diluted with water and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The separated solid crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 186°–87°. (Found : C, 84.41; H, 5.42. $C_{22}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 84.61; H, 5.23%).

The acetyl derivative : Prepared as usual and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in light yellow needles (0.3 g.) gave m.p. 180°–81°. (Found : C, 81.25; H, 4.98. $C_{22}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 81.36; H, 5.08%).

2'-Phenyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') pyran-4'-one : 2-Hydroxy-1-fluorenyl styryl ketone (1 g.) in alcohol (100 ml.) was refluxed with conc. hydrochloric acid for 36 hr. The solvent was removed and the solid obtained crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in colourless cubes (0.4 g.), m.p. 156°. (Found : C, 84.78; H, 4.98. $C_{22}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 84.61; H, 5.13%).

2'-Phenyl fluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone : 2-Hydroxy-1-fluorenyl styryl ketone (1 g.) in iso-amyl alcohol (20 ml.) was refluxed with selenium dioxide

(3 g.) in an oil bath at 140°–150° for 15 hr. It was then filtered hot and iso-amyl alcohol was removed by steam distillation. The residue obtained crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in yellow needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 259°. (Found : C, 85.29; H, 4.52. $C_{22}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 85.15; H, 4.47%).

2-Hydroxy-1-fluorenyl p-methoxy styryl ketone : A mixture of 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorene (1.5 g.), potassium hydroxide (8 g. in 8 ml. water) and anisaldehyde (1.5 ml) in alcohol (100 ml.) was left overnight at room temperature. It was then diluted and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate and water. It crystallised from benzene in yellow needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 169°–70°. (Found : C, 80.87; H, 5.29. $C_{23}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 80.70; H, 5.26%).

The acetyl derivative : Prepared as usual and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in light yellow needles gave m.p. 194°. (Found : C, 78.60; H, 5.43. $C_{25}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 78.12; H, 5.21%).

2'-(p-Methoxy phenyl) fluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') pyran-4'-one : 2-Hydroxy-1-fluorenyl p-methoxy styryl ketone (1 g.) was refluxed in alcoholic solution with conc. hydrochloric acid (10 ml.) for 36 hr. The alcohol was removed and the residue obtained crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in light yellow needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 194°. (Found : C, 80.63; H, 5.62. $C_{23}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 80.70; H, 5.26%).

2'-(p-Methoxy phenyl) fluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone : 2-Hydroxy-1-fluorenyl p-methoxy styryl ketone (1 g.) was refluxed in iso-amyl alcohol with selenium dioxide (3 g.) in an oil bath at 140°–50° for 15 hr. The product obtained on working up as before crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 251°. (Found : C, 81.43; H, 4.76. $C_{23}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 81.17; H, 4.70%).

2-Hydroxy 9-oxo-1-fluorenyl styryl ketone : A mixture of 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorenone (1 g.) in alcohol (100 ml.), potassium hydroxide (5 g. in 5 ml. water) and benzaldehyde (1 ml.) was kept overnight at room temperature. The dark red solution obtained was diluted and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The separated solid crystallised from xylene in red prisms (0.4 g.), m.p. 229°–30°. (Found : C, 81.12; H, 4.31. $C_{22}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 80.98; H, 4.29%).

The acetyl derivative : Prepared as usual and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles gave m.p. 169°. (Found : C, 78.43; H, 4.08. $C_{24}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 78.27; H, 4.34%).

2'-Phenyl 9-oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') pyran-4'-one : 2-Hydroxy 9-oxo-1-fluorenyl styryl ketone (1 g.) in alcohol (150 ml.) was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (15 ml.) on a steam bath for 48 hr. The solvent

was removed and residue crystallised from benzene in yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 196°. (Found : C, 81.16; H, 4.29. $C_{22}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 80.98; H, 4.29%).

2'-Phenyl-9-oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone : 2-Hydroxy 9-oxo-1-fluorenyl styryl ketone (1 g.) was refluxed in iso-amyl alcohol (50 ml.) with selenium dioxide (3 g.) at 140°–50° for 15 hr. It was then filtered hot, and iso-amyl alcohol was removed by steam distillation. The residue crystallised from xylene in orange prisms (0.3 g.), m.p. 286°. (Found : C, 81.17; H, 3.84. $C_{22}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 81.47; H, 3.70%).

2-Hydroxy 9-oxo-1-fluorenyl p-methoxy styryl ketone : A mixture of 2-hydroxy-1-acetyl fluorenone (1 g.) in alcohol (100 ml.), potassium hydroxide (5 g. in 5 ml. water) and anisaldehyde (1 ml.) was kept at room temperature for 24 hr. It was then diluted and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained crystallised from xylene in red prisms (0.4 g.), m.p. 238°. (Found : C, 77.23; H, 4.67. $C_{23}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 77.54; H, 4.49%).

The Acetyl derivative : Prepared as usual and crystallised from benzene in orange needles gave m.p. 177°. (Found : C, 75.61; H, 4.45. $C_{25}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 75.37; H, 4.53%).

2'-(p-Methoxy phenyl) 9-oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5')-pyran-4'-one : 2-Hydroxy 9-oxo-1-fluorenyl p-methoxy styryl ketone (1 g.) in alcohol (200 ml.) was refluxed with conc. hydrochloric acid (20 ml.) for 48 hr. The solvent was then removed and the residue crystallised from benzene in orange prisms (0.4 g.), m.p. 220°. (Found : C, 77.39; H, 4.53. $C_{23}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 77.54; H, 4.49%).

2'-(p-Methoxy phenyl)-9-oxofluoreno (2, 1 : 6', 5') γ -pyrone : 2-Hydroxy-9-oxo-1-fluorenyl p-methoxy styryl ketone (1 g.) was refluxed in iso-amyl alcohol (50 ml.) with selenium dioxide (3 g.) in an oil bath at 140°–50° for 15 hr. and then filtered hot. The solvent was removed by steam distillation and the residue was crystallised from xylene in orange cubes (0.3 g.), m.p. 296°. (Found : C, 78.21; H, 3.50. $C_{23}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 77.96; H, 3.95%).

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